

Modified UWB Antenna for Cognitive Radio Applications

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Abstract

In this study, an integrated dual port ultra-wide band (UWB) and narrow band (NB) antennas for cognitive radio (CR) application are reviewed. In this paper, a monopole circular antenna is used for UWB sensing antenna fed by coplanar waveguide (CPW) transmission line with rectangular ground plane. The etched “e” shaped micro-strip antenna is basically used for NB as communication purposes, having low surface current density. This integrated antenna is a potential element for CR application, where circular monopole covers the UWB frequency band (3.1GHz to 10.6GHz) for spectrum sensing and NB having two resonant frequencies of 4.8GHz and 5.8GHz for WLAN application in mobile, laptops and wireless adapters operating at C- band. The return loss is less than -10dB in the whole operating band.

Keywords - Ultra wide band (UWB), narrow band (NB), cognitive radio (CR), coplanar waveguide (CPW).

I. INTRODUCTION

This document is a template. For the communication system, electromagnetic spectrum plays crucial role. It is kind of natural resource, used as transmitter and receiver efficiently declared by government [1]. As we know electromagnetic spectrum is very vast having the problem of congestion and interference, for this cognitive radio comes under consideration to avoid above problems [2-10]. In such a way, dynamic spectrum management process applied, in which radio signal having the intelligence power to detect the available channel in the spectrum then corresponding changes the features and parameters of transmission and reception in a given band at same location. It is most promising technique for wireless application which makes wireless and radio network fully cognitive. A cognitive radio is “continuously monitoring its own action” in addition to “finding the radio application”.

Radio spectrum consists of various numbers of bands, in which ultra wide band having frequency range from 3.1GHz to 10.6GHz (bandwidth=7.5GHz), occupies a very wide bandwidth with the feature of Gigabits/sec data rate. UWB also known as digital wireless pulse used for transmits maximum number of data over the broad spectrum of frequency band, UWB

carrying low power consumption as less than 0.5milliwatts for short distance up to 230 feet to achieve high bandwidth connections [11-20]. This bandwidth implies to cause of interference, just because of it will easily cross the boundaries of many present licensed carrier based transmissions, and low power spectral density function. UWB includes several of advantages as robustness for multipath fading, low power transmission and dissipation. It is also having some similar characteristics like wireless technology that might allow it to coexist with various networking standard LAN, MAN & WAN.

Narrow band implies to data and telecommunication services and tools that having narrow set of frequencies in communication channels. It is generally used to carry out the voice data audio spectrum that accepts the restricted frequency range. The federal communication commission (FCC) has approved the use of UWB technology for commercial purposes and FCC also allocated specific range of frequency as 50cps to 64kbps for mobile communication on 14th February, 2002 [21-22].

II. STATE OF ART

It is kind of integrated antenna for cognitive radio having UWB for sensing and monitoring the spectrum and narrow band NB for communication purposes. For the non fading environment the capacity of communication channel can be derived as:-

$$C = B * \log_2 \left[1 + \frac{S}{N} \right] \quad (1)$$

C= channel capacity. (Bit/sec)

B= channel bandwidth (Hz)

S= signal power (watts)

N= noise power (watts)

From the above equations, refer that capacity C is directly proportional to B and S, and inversely proportional to N. As the UWB system having the issue of interference from other wireless technology but this complication can be diminish by adaptive selection of frequency band in assorted band UWB system. The wide band antenna used for feeding the receiver for spectrum sensing [23].

III. ANTENNA DESIGN

This is kind of integrated antenna system combines with UWB for sensing the spectrum and NB for transmission and reception purpose. Here the new integration technique takes place where one antenna having large metallization space which is efficiently shared by additional antenna. The present design is two port antenna system where port 1 consist of coplanar waveguide (CPW) fed circularly monopole radiating patch [24] as the first antenna performing UWB operations and port 2 consist of coaxial fed “e” shape micro-strip slot antenna achieve narrow band NB applications as second antenna providing dual purpose operations. Both antennas are working simultaneously aiming to space of low current concentration. Here port 1 circular monopole behaves as coplanar ground for second “e” shape antenna for narrow band at port 2. In this way, such kind of approach provides dual band communication for CR application. The proposed dual antenna geometry is designed and simulated by using Ansys High Frequency Structural Simulator (HFSS.14) [25].

In this defined integrated antenna design, reported in [26], is examine as a reference design and then further refinements are carried out to enhance the performance. The UWB and NB antennas are printed on a very compact FR-4 epoxy substrate of the dimensions of 30mm*30mm*1.6mm as shown in fig.1. The FR-4 epoxy substrate having relative permittivity $\epsilon_r = 4.4$, relative permeability $\mu_r = 1$ and dielectric loss tangent $\tan \Theta = 0.025$. The width of micro-strip is optimized for impedance matching of 50Ω. The radius of circular patch can be defined by formula considering lower resonant frequency as 3.1 GHz.

$$L.F. = \frac{7.2}{2.25 * R + g} \quad (2)$$

Where L.F. = lower resonant frequency in GHz, R= radius of circular patch in centimeters, g= gap in centimeters between patch and ground plane.

The radius of patch determine the variation in return loss as increase in the radius, resonance gets shifted towards lower frequency [27]. The design analysis and optimization of antenna were performed using finite element method (FEM) based up on HFSS simulator.

The design approach includes two antenna systems. The first antenna is CPW fed circular monopole provide high impedance matching over wider bandwidth. The second antenna placed on the same substrate etched “e” shape micro-strip fed by coaxial feeding technique incorporated very good isolation and mutual coupling between the ports [28,29].

Fig.1. Proposed dual port integrated UWB and NB antenna system top view

Fig.2. Proposed dual port “e” shape etched integrated antenna system bottom view

TABLE I
Antenna Parameters

Parameters	Values (mm)
W	30
L	30
R	10.5
A	14
B	9
C	8
D	6
E	3
F	5

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

The simulation of prototype antenna done by HFSS to activates the communication in bandwidth from 3.1GHz to 10.6 GHz. The simulated reflection

coefficient for UWB and NB antenna describe by S_{11} and S_{22} parameter respectively in fig [3].The NB resonates at two frequency 4.8GHz and 5.8GHz used for WLAN mobile, laptop and wireless adapters also. Additionally, the reflection coefficient S_{11} and S_{22} value below -10dB indicates the frequency region where antenna can radiate electromagnetic energy efficiently [30].

Fig.3. Reflection coefficient of integrated antenna system

V. CONCLUSION

From the above discussion and result analysis, it can be concluded that integrated antenna for cognitive radio application provides better performance in terms of high data rates and bandwidth compared to other. In sequence to get rid of interference between UWB and communication NB such as WLAN and C- band communication system, a simple integrated antenna with two notch band for UWB application is designed in this paper and simulated result shoes the better agreement for cognitive radio application.

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